

The Challenges and Impact of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education as Perceived by the Primary Level Teachers of Amai Pakpak Central Elementary School

Sittie-Asia U. Macarimbor^{1*}, Sittie Jannah G. Hassan¹
¹Mindanao State University – Main Campus
macarimbor.su921@s.msumain.edu.ph

Date Submitted:
January 30, 2026

Date Accepted:
March 14, 2026

Date Published:
March 21, 2026

DOI:
10.5281/zenodo.19151641

ABSTRACT

One of the recent transitions in the Philippine educational system brought by K-12 program is the Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE), which has already materialized for already twelve years. The initiation of this new language policy is also an advent of different challenges affecting its implementation, and its effectiveness as assessed by the primary teachers towards their knowledge, the learning materials, and the attitudes on the policy implementation. In this study, the researchers revealed the factors/problems affecting the primary level teachers, whom were considered as the main constituent towards the attainment of the

objectives of MTB-MLE. The goal of the authors is to gather and analyze adequate data on the primary level teachers. With this, researchers accommodate 75% of primary level teachers' population from each primary grade level of Amai Pakpak Central Elementary School (APCES). The findings of the study revealed that the average mean of how teachers perceived the challenges brought by MTB-MLE is slightly serious. Furthermore, it is revealed that the most major problem they had encountered since the implementation of the new language policy is the need to cope with the lacks of mother tongue vocabularies in translating highly technical terms especially in Mathematics and Science. This obstacle has posed difficulties for teachers in effectively teaching these subjects. Lastly, the study explored the teachers' perceived levels of knowledge, availability of materials, and attitudes towards MTB-MLE. The findings can contribute to the improvement and refinement of the MTB-MLE program, enhancing its effectiveness in promoting multilingual education in the Philippines. By unlocking the overall percentage of the perceived level of knowledge, materials, and attitudes, the researcher aimed to assess the impact of the implementation of MTB-MLE in this respective elementary institution.

Keywords: *Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education, language policy, Philippines, Primary Level Teachers, Multilingualism.*

INTRODUCTION

One of the features of Basic Education Curriculum brought about by the new K to 12 programs is Mother Tongue -Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) which is introduced particularly in Kindergarten, Grades 1, 2 and 3. MTB-MLE, or Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education refers to the utilization of the language spoken by the learner at home, along with two or more other languages (Filipino and English), as a primary means of instruction in school. Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education is the government's banner program for education as a salient part of the implementation of the K to 12 Basic Education Program. Based on the studies done by various institutions in the Philippines, the use of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB- MLE) show that being competent in the student's lingua franca makes it more effective for them in learning additional languages; in fact, it let them more than prepared. Thus, he better understands concepts if taught in their dialect or lingua franca. The program may look promising however, it faces a lot of challenges especially in the primary level, kinder to grade 3.

It recognizes the value of incorporating familiar languages into the learning process to enhance students' educational experience. In DepEd Order No. 74, s. 2009 otherwise known as Institutionalizing Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MLE) strengthens mother tongue as medium of instruction in the primary grades. In the Philippine educational system, MT is also offered as a subject in the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum which started in 2012 (RA 10533). The Department of Education said that the teachers are hired in their own locality, giving them a background on the languages of the pupils enrolled in the school of the locality.

The City of Marawi is located in the Lanao Del Sur and most of the people speaks Meranao language. Amai Pakpak Central Elementary School is one of the public elementary school in Marawi City and majority of the learners are Meranao and is Meranao speakers. As such, Meranao is the official mother tongue subject and language used as medium of instruction in the area.

In particular, there is no officially published study conducted in the City of Marawi which focuses on the challenges and impact of primary level teacher on the implementation of MTB-MLE in Amai Pakpak Central Elementary School (APCES), which drives the researchers to conduct this study. This research sought to establish the perceived challenges and the effectiveness of the MTBMLE throughout the policy implementation of the primary level teachers in the City Schools Division of Marawi, the Amai Pakpak Central Elementary School towards the use of the Mother Tongue (MT) as a medium of instruction in primary level learners, specifically from Kinder 1 up to Grades 1, 2, and 3.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Mother Tongue Based – Multilingual Education curriculum welcomes additional challenging tasks for teachers (Medilo, 2016). In a macro-perspective, we take a look at the whole education system of the Philippines. Gonzales (1996) describes the situation of Philippine education as a result of its multilingual background and the implementation of its diverse policies. It stems from the unequal status

of the two languages used in the bilingual policy – Filipino and English. By this, the vernacular assists the use of these two languages by providing a bridge or a transitional medium of instruction.

As Nolasco (2010) mentioned, teaching in the MTB-MLE requires deep background on varied teaching strategies. The teacher plays the most crucial role in the education of the child as a mentor and facilitator of learning. However, the teachers should make sure that they are empowered well enough to implement these approaches and these are aligned with the changing needs of times. As cited by Freeman and Freeman (2000), teachers' abilities to clearly articulate their precepts, and opinions, about what makes learning happen in an integral part of their effectiveness as educator. These precepts become the vessel within which all future teaching ideas are contained and the perspective through which new ideas are filtered.

Gaylo (2020) demonstrated that the limited vocabulary makes implementing MTB-MLE goals difficult. Certain students may have limited comprehension of the language being used. Adriano et al. (2021) identified several difficulties, such as a lack of textbooks and dictionaries that made it particularly difficult to teach and achieve immediate success with MTB-MLE implementation, as teachers are unfamiliar with the terminology used.

Tonio and Ella (2019) discussed the difficulties encountered when translating technical terms in MTB-MLE, such as in Science and Mathematics subjects. As a result, Abrea et al. (2020) stated that students have difficulty comprehending lectures, which challenges teachers' translation abilities.

As cited by Luis Enrique López, Dutcher (2001) that in the case of the Philippines, MTB-MLE may not necessary be as attractive as it sounds because one classroom can easily have the representation of more than five linguistic backgrounds. This seems to be more challenging in such multilingual settings (Ghimire, 2012), unlike settings where both students and teachers share the same local language (Kang, 2012).

In the study of Ababa-balang (2012) stated that through the use of the children's first language, students can learn and understand basic concepts, ideas skills and processes. In addition, Barcelona on 2012 stated that in mother tongue approach have gained mastery of the subject matter. He also proved that the students taught using MTB-MLE performed differently and better than those students who expose to conventional teaching strategy.

In the case of MTB-MLE in the Philippines, Mahboob and Cruz (2013) believe that the success of MTB-MLE will highly depend on the change in attitude towards languages. This is a conclusion they reached after their study revealed some positive attitude towards the MTB-MLE policy.

The researchers sought to answer the overarching research question of the Challenges and Impact of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education as perceived by the Primary Level Teachers of Amai Pakpak Central Elementary School. The two specific questions are as follows:

1. What are the Challenges experienced by the Primary Level Teachers in Amai Pakpak Central Elementary School towards the use of MTB-MLE?

2. How do teachers find the effectiveness of MTB-MLE Implementation in Amai Pakpak Central Elementary School?

Theoretical Framework

The purpose of this study is to explore the perceptions of primary level teachers towards the use of MTB-MLE in Amai Pakpak Central Elementary School. Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) is an educational policy that promotes the use of students' mother tongue as the medium of instruction in the early years of schooling. This theoretical framework will draw upon both Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs by Abraham Maslow and Language Policy Theory by Bernard Spolsky.

Maslow's Theory suggests that individuals have a hierarchy of needs that must be fulfilled in order to reach their full potential. In this study, Maslow's Theory of Hierarchy of needs can provide valuable insights into the challenges perceived by the primary level teachers. According to this theory, if the individual has satisfied the primary needs, more likely that he will maximize and optimize all potentials he has. By incorporating this theory, this study can explore the impact of these challenges on the teachers' attitude and motivation towards the MTB-MLE implementation. This supports the claims that if the teachers do not have access to instructional materials or professional development opportunities, such as knowledge and skills through seminars and training, it can hinder their ability to reach their full potential as educators.

Language Policy Theory by Bernard Spolsky, refers to the decisions and actions taken by governments or institutions regarding language use in various contexts, such as education. The Language Policy Theory is a framework that examines how language policies impact educational practices and outcomes. It focuses on the role of language policies in shaping teaching methods, student learning, and overall educational experiences.

This theory will provide insights in the study on how the implementation of the program shape the primary level teachers' teaching methods employed in the school, the languages used for instruction, and the impact of the challenges they face. Considering this theory, it can examine how language policies, such as the implementation of MTB-MLE, influence the teaching practices and experiences of teachers. This provides the understanding of the challenges teachers face in adapting to the language policy, the impact of the policy on their instructional strategies, and the overall effectiveness of the policy in achieving its intended goals.

Significance of the study

The program faces several challenges such as those concerning resources, materials, and curriculum (Awid, 2010). In this study, the researchers aim to take a look at the challenges and impact of MTBMLE in a particular institution, Amai Pakpak Central Elementary School (APCES). By examining the challenges faced by the primary level teachers in APCES, the implementation MTB-MLE will be able to enhance awareness to the teachers and the school division to improve the implementation of mother tongue-based multilingual education. This study would benefit the following:

A. Students

This study can be beneficial to the students in a way that once the challenges were address and resolve, it creates positive ripple effects on students. They become more participative in activities and discussions, leading to increased engagement and attentiveness. This students' active involvement can enhance enhance learning experience and overall academic performance.

B. Teachers

This study will be a tool to recognize their difficulties upon the implementation of MTB-MLE. Wherein, teachers will become more aware of the obstacles they face, and can work together with the school division to improve their practices and strengthen the implementation of MTB-MLE.

C. Stakeholders/Implementers

Through this study, they can be aware and able to know the problems as especially the major problem encountered by the teachers in the implementation of MTB-MLE and can able to plan better actions for the policy to be sustainable and successful.

METHODOLOGY

This chapter explains the methodology employed in this study to answer the overarching research question of the challenges, and the impact and/or the effectiveness of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education as perceived by the Primary Level Teachers of Amai Pakpak Central Elementary School.

Research Design

A mixed approach was used for this study as a method of investigation. For the first research question, the researchers utilized a qualitative research approach to explore the experienced challenges and perspectives of the primary level teachers. According to Travers (1981), this descriptive research design has two principal aims; (1) to describe the nature of a situation as it exists at the time of the study- which is a relevant approach to provide a comprehensive understanding of the considered challenges as perceived by the teachers, and (2) to explore the causes of a particular phenomenon, as this aim helps understand the reason of the occurrence of the challenges, and the factors that contribute to it. Whereas, for the second research question that aims to answer the impact and/or effectiveness of MTBMLE, the researchers engaged in a quantitative research approach.

Research Setting

The survey was conducted at Amai Pakpak Central Elementary School located in Brgy. Datu Saber Marawi City, in the province of Lanao del Sur which involved the primary level teachers in the institution. This was selected purposefully as this is categorized as one of the populated and known

elementary school inside the City of Marawi. As Merriam (1998) and Stake (2000) strongly stated that the most important part of case study research is the appropriate selection of cases.

Participants

A total of thirty-two (32) primary level teachers of Amai Pakpak Central Elementary School were involved as a respondent in this study. The researchers utilized Convenience sampling, aiming at least seventy five percent (75%) of the total teachers' population from each grade level as a representative sample from kinder 1 to Grade 3, and had answered the survey-questionnaire administered. Furthermore, selected primary level teachers undergo in the oral interview.

Instrumentation

In this study, the researchers employed a mixed-methods approach by incorporating two distinct but related adapted survey questionnaire as an instrument:

First, an adapted-modified survey questionnaire from Gorio et al. (2014). The items in the questionnaire are actual indicators of the challenges they faced in the implementation of MTB-MLE. This includes (1) the respondent's profile which includes the name (optional), name of school as workplace, age and as well as the gender, (2) shows the degree of seriousness of problems perceived/assessed by the teachers in the implementation of mother tongue. Respondents were asked to rate each item in the questionnaire using four-point scale, and (3) shows which among various factors they consider as the major problem that they were greatly affected to. Along with this, the use of oral interview as an instrument that includes a series of carefully crafted questions. This is to gather relevant data that will be used to support the claims in the findings.

The second part of the questionnaire was a Quantitative Participatory Method by Davies and Dart (2005), which used to conduct the study where the participants were required to answer the survey with yes or no. The question involves the Mother Tongue Based-Multilingual Education's Knowledge of the Participants, Instructional Materials being used, and Attitudes of Participants; this will undergo to measure the overall impact and effectivity of the MTB-MLE Implementation. By incorporating these two questionnaires, the researchers gathered comprehensive insights and captured a holistic understanding of the research study.

Data Collection Procedure

The researcher prepared the research design and tools to be utilized in the study. Permission from the principal to gather data from the kinder to grade 3 teachers was obtained after the approval of the researcher's professor to conduct the study. Obtaining the total number of respondents was also done to prepare the needed numbers of questionnaire. With proper consultation, the researchers obtained schedule for the administration of the questionnaire. Distribution and retrieval were personally executed by the researchers. Upon approval, permission from the School Division Superintendent, District Planning

Officer, and School Head was secured before the actual gathering of data, with the proper recommendation of the Quality Assurance Officer.

Data were collected through various sources which includes surveys, short period of classroom observations, and individual interviews. The researchers personally administered the questionnaire to the teachers. Thereafter the survey, the data gathered were tallied, tabulated, interpreted and analysed presented using tables and texts.

Method of Analysis

The gathered data were organized, tabulated and illustrated in a series of tables. To analyze the research findings of the first research question, the researchers engaged in thematic analysis. In creating themes, the researcher carefully read the answers in both survey questionnaire and the interview transcript to identify the recurring themes, ideas, issues, and/or concept that emerge; this patterns from the listed responses help accommodate the qualitative data presented. The descriptive measures utilized to address the problems were frequency, ranking and weighted mean. Moreover, descriptive statistical analysis method was used as a method of analysis for the second research question. This is to draw conclusions from data collected in the Survey Questionnaire. After gathering the data, the researchers used frequency and percentage to come up with the findings.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the data and information gathered by the researchers in relation to the study. Also presented are the analyses and interpretations of tabulated results in answer to the specific problems of the study.

PROBLEMS	MEAN	DESCRIPTION
a) Lacks of training and workshops	2.81	Moderately Serious
b) Experiences scarcity of teachers' references	2.81	Moderately Serious
c) Lacks knowledge on how to speak the dialect of the pupils.	1.90	Slightly Serious
d) Experiences difficulties in his/her teaching strategies considering the MTB – MLE.	2.31	Slightly Serious
e) Lacks mother tongue vocabularies in translating highly technical terms especially in mathematics and science.	2.62	Moderately Serious
f) Needs to cope with the national test since these are given in English and in Filipino (MTAP, NAT and the like)	2.59	Moderately Serious
Average	2.50	Slightly Serious

Legend: 3.26 - 4.00 Very Serious (VS)
 2.51 – 3.25 Moderately Serious (MS)

1.76 – 2.50	Slightly Serious (SS)
1.00 – 1.75	Not Serious (NS)

Table 1 illustrated the different factors/problems encountered by the primary level teachers in the implementation of MTB-MLE. With the description provided, these following were considered as moderately serious: In this twelve-year old language policy, the teachers still experienced first, the lack of trainings and workshops, as indicated by a mean score of 2.81. It appears in the interview transcript that this highlights the need for professional development opportunities for teachers to enhance their knowledge and skills in implementing MTB-MLE effectively. Furthermore, the scarcity of teachers' references, also with a mean score of 2.81, underscores the importance of readily available resources that support teachers in delivering instruction in the mother tongue. This factor emphasizes the need for curriculum materials, textbooks, and other references that align with the MTB-MLE approach. Additionally, the lack of mother tongue vocabularies for highly technical terms, particularly in mathematics and science (mean score of 2.62), poses a significant challenge. This finding align with the responses as the respondents admits that efforts should be made to develop and provide comprehensive mother tongue vocabularies that encompass a wide range of technical concepts, enabling effective communication and understanding in these subjects. Lastly, the need to cope with national tests, which are written in either English or Filipino (MTAP, NAT and the like) with the mean score of 2.59, this highlights the tension between the mother tongue-based instruction and the language used in national assessments. This factor emphasizes the importance of aligning assessment practices with the goals and principles of MTB-MLE to ensure fair and accurate evaluation of students' learning outcomes.

Whereas, it appears that the lack of knowledge on how to speak the dialect of the students (mean score of 1.90) and the difficulties experienced in adapting teaching strategies to MTB-MLE (mean score of 2.31) were perceived as slightly serious challenges. While these factors may not be as prominent as the others, they still warrant attention and support to ensure effective implementation of MTB-MLE. This result align on what the Department of Education said that the teachers are hired in their own locality, giving them a background on the languages of the pupils enrolled in the school of the locality. With this, the teachers do not find too much difficulty on this problem since they are only assigned in the areas that they are capable of speaking the specific dialect of the students.

Overall, the degree of seriousness of the factors/problems in the implementation of the MTB-MLE as to the teachers was revealed as moderately serious. As Gorio et al. (2014) conforms that there are many issues to consider one of these are the teachers, since they are one factor affecting the implementation of MTB-MLE. With this, the factors/problems that are soberly bothering them should be treated in order for the implementation of MTB-MLE be sustainable as well as the objectives of the said policy would be attained. This also implies that teachers found the factors not that easy to handle with since the factors/problems brought by the new language policy had a moderate effect to them thus it manifests that teachers do need help to lessen the seriousness of the factors brought by the new language policy.

Table 2. Teachers’ Most Major Problem in the Implementation of MTB-MLE

PROBLEMS	FREQUENCY	RANK
a) Lacks of training and workshops	7	Second
b) Experiences scarcity of teachers’ references	6	3 rd
c) Lacks knowledge on how to speak the dialect of the pupils	3	4 th
d) Experiences difficulties in his/her teaching strategies considering the MTB – MLE.	2	5th
e) Lacks mother tongue vocabularies in translating highly technical terms especially in mathematics and science.	11	1st
f) Needs to cope with the national test since these are given in English and in Filipino (MTAP, NAT and the like)	3	4 th
TOTAL	32	

Table 2 revealed the major problem which the teachers are currently experiencing since the implementation of MTB-MLE. Out of 32 respondents, it is evident that a significant challenge in the implementation of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTBMLE) is the *lack of mother tongue vocabularies in translating highly technical terms within subjects such as mathematics and science*. This challenge was reported by 11 out of 32 respondents, indicating its salience. Gaylo (2020) demonstrated that the limited vocabulary makes implementing MTB-MLE goals difficult. The absence of these vocabularies can impede students' comprehension and engagement in these subjects, which are vital for their academic advancement.

Another noteworthy obstacle, as indicated by 7 respondents, is the *lack of training and workshops*. This signifies that teachers may not have sufficient support or resources to effectively incorporate MTBMLE into their instructional practices. Adriano et al. (2021) identified several difficulties, such as a lack of textbooks and dictionaries that made it particularly difficult to teach and achieve immediate success with MTB-MLE implementation, as teachers are unfamiliar with the terminology used. With this claim, the *scarcity of teachers' references*, identified by 6 respondents, suggests a paucity of available materials or guidance for teachers to consult when delivering instruction in the mother tongue. Additionally, 3 respondents highlighted the challenge of *lacking proficiency in the dialect spoken by the students*. This can further hinder effective communication and instruction. Addressing this challenge is imperative to ensure that teachers can engage effectively with their students and establish an optimal learning environment. Another 3 respondents also emphasized the *need to navigate national tests that are written in English or Filipino*. This adds an additional layer of pressure for both teachers and students, as they must navigate between the mother tongue-based instruction and the language of the national assessments. This challenge underscores the importance of aligning the curriculum and assessment methods to support the successful implementation of MTBMLE.

On the contrary, the least prevalent challenge reported was from 2 respondents which experienced *difficulties in his/her teaching strategies considering the MTB – MLE*. Although this may not be as

prominent, it still warrants attention as it suggests that some teachers may encounter challenges in adjusting their instructional approaches to effectively integrate the mother tongue into their teaching practices. As Nolasco (2010) mentioned, teaching in the MTB-MLE requires deep background on varied teaching strategies.

Table 3. The Knowledge of the Primary Level Teachers in Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education

MTB-MLE KNOWLEDGE		YES		NO	
Statement		f	%	f	%
1	I understand the benefits of MTB-MLE.	31	96.875%	1	3.125%
2	I am oriented about the MTB-MLE.	30	93.75%	2	6.25%
3	I have enough information about the MTB-MLE.	26	81.25%	6	18.75%
4	I am adequately equipped with knowledge about how to carry out the MTB-MLE.	24	75.0%	8	25.0%
5	I am fluent in the language used in MTB-MLE.	26	81.25%	6	18.75%
6	My first language is Meranao.	30	93.75%	2	6.25%
AVERAGE		87.00%		13.00%	

Table 3 provides the information on the knowledge of the primary level teachers in MTB-MLE. The results show that, majority of the teachers understand the benefits of MTB-MLE, with thirty-one (31) out of thirty-two (32) participants answered affirmatively. According to Maslow's Theory, individuals have a hierarchy of needs that must be fulfilled in order to reach their full potential. Based on the results provided, 87 percent of the primary level teachers are equipped with the knowledge about MTB-MLE. This supports the claim that the teachers in Amai Pakpak Central Elementary School (APCES) are trained enough to teach the MTB-MLE however, as shown in the table 1 lacks of trainings and workshops is still one of the considered moderately serious problems in the implementation of the program. This concludes that the knowledge of the teachers in APCES are moderate but they have the enough information about the MTB-MLE. Based on the information provided in the table 3, most of the participants are Meranao and twenty-six (26) out of thirty (30) Meranao speaking teachers are fluent in the language used in teaching MTB-MLE.

Table 4. Instructional Materials that is being used in Teaching the Mother Tongue

INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS		YES		NO	
Statement		f	%	f	%
1	Manuals for Mother- Tongue are provided.	27	84.37%	5	15.62%
2	The lesson in the manuals is easy to follow.	24	75.00%	8	25.00%
3	There are enough materials other than teachers' manuals to aid the pupils in learning the mother-tongue.	20	62.50%	12	37.50%
4	Various teaching strategies are specified in the manuals.	23	71.87%	9	28.12%
5	There are enough manuals provided to use for Mother-Tongue.	16	50.00%	16	50.00%
6	Time specified in the manuals is enough to carry out the content.	24	75.00%	8	25.00%

AVERAGE	69.80%	30.20%
----------------	---------------	---------------

Table 4 shows that, most of the participants answered affirmatively, in which led the researchers to conclude that the instructional materials used in teaching mother tongue in the primary level in APCES are provided. According to Maslow’s theory, if the individual has satisfied the primary needs, more likely that he will maximize and optimize all potentials he has. Based on the table provided, the overall results with a total average of 69.80 percent, the instructional materials to teach the MTB-MLE in the primary level in APCES are given that the primary level teachers are able to reach their full potential to teach the Mother Tongue. However, in the statement number five, there is an equal distribution of positive and negative responses. This indicates that the participants have different perception regarding the adequacy of manuals provided to use for mother tongue as an instruction.

Table 5. Attitudes of the Primary Level Teachers towards the Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education

ATTITUDES TOWARDS MTB-MLE		YES		NO	
Statement	f	%	f	%	%
1 I am positively supporting the MTB-MLE program.	27	96.87%	5	3.12%	
2 I support mother-tongue teaching.	29	93.75%	3	6.25%	
3 I positively like the lessons in mother-tongue.	28	81.25%	4	18.75%	
4 I am happy for the MTB-MLE program.	29	75.00%	3	25.00%	
5 I know than MTB-MLE positively affects attendance.	23	81.25%	9	18.75%	
AVERAGE		85.62%		14.37%	

Table 5 intends to show the attitudes of the teachers towards mother tongue based- multilingual education. The researchers found out that majority of the teachers in Amai Pakpak Central Elementary School (APCES) have positive feelings towards MTB-MLE. The results shows that twenty-seven (27) out of thirty-two (32) participants positively supports MTB-MLE. And according to Mahboob and Cruz (2013), the success of MTB-MLE will highly depend on the change in attitude towards languages. Their study revealed some positive attitude towards the MTB-MLE policy. Based on the results of this table, the overall total average of 85.625 percent participants answered affirmatively. This claims that MTB-MLE implementation in APCES have a positive impact towards the attitudes of the primary level teachers.

The findings of the study have concluded that the primary level teachers in Amai Pakpak Central Elementary Schools faces a various challenge, however, these challenges are not a hindrance in the effectiveness of the MTB-MLE implementation.

CONCLUSION

The findings of the study have shed light on the various challenges faced by teachers in implementing MTB-MLE. After analyzing the gathered data, based on the results of the survey questionnaire and the selected oral interviews, it was found that one of the major challenges faced by the teachers is the lack of training and workshops. This means that the teachers are not receiving sufficient professional development opportunities to enhance their understanding and implementation of MTB-MLE. Another challenge identified is the absence of translated highly technical terms, which can make it difficult for teachers to effectively communicate complex concepts to students.

To conclude this study, it is encouraging to note that the primary level teachers in Amai Pakpak Central Elementary School (APCES) have a moderate level of knowledge about MTB-MLE. This suggests that they have received some form of training and are equipped with the necessary information to teach in the mother tongue. While the knowledge level may not be extensive, it is still a positive indication of their preparedness. In terms of instructional materials, the findings revealed that while these are provided, it is not considered sufficient. This implies that there may be a need for more resources and materials that are specifically tailored to the needs of MTB-MLE classrooms. Despite the challenges the teachers perceived, primary level teachers maintain a positive attitude towards the program. This suggests that they recognize the value and importance of MTB-MLE, even in the face of difficulties. It showcases their dedication and commitment to providing quality education to their students. As Freeman and Freeman (2000) states that, "teachers abilities to clearly articulate their precepts, and opinions, about what makes learning happen is an integral part of their effectiveness as educator." It can be seen that the implementation of the MTB-MLE have effectively impacted the perception of the primary level teachers in APCES.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the teachers' recommendations done in the oral interviews, in order to enhance the policy implementation, school divisions and superintendent should encourage: (1) more trainings, seminars and projects for the teachers (2) produce localized instructional books in mother tongue (3) materials to be used in teaching the MTB-MLE. These suggestions align in accordance to Spolsky (2004), it is "what people think should be done" (p. 14). By this, suggestions by the teachers should be consider to improve the implementation of the MTB-MLE as they are the main implementer of the said policy. As stated by Rosekrans, Sherris and Chatry-Komerek (2012), the problems encountered in the implementation of MTB-MLE can be overcome by "progressive power of change".

REFERENCES

- Ababa-Balang Vivien. (2012). The effectiveness of Mother Tongue Based Curriculum on the proficiency level in mathematics of grade one 0pupils of San Antonio Elementary School, Iriga City South District, School Year 2012-2013.
- Adriano, M. N. I., Franco, N. T., & Estrella, E. A. (2021). Language-in-education policies and stakeholders' perception of the current MTB-MLE policy in an ASEAN country. *Australian Journal of Language and Literacy*, 44(1), 84-99.
- Awid, M. (2010, Nov). MLE in the Philippines. Paper presented at the MTB-MLE Forum, Chiang Mai, Thailand. Organization.www.unesco.org/education.Accessed Dec. 23, 2011.
- Barcelona, Sonia G. (2012). Mother tongue-based multilingual education in teaching mathematics among selected grade six students in Southville I Elementary School, District of Cabuyao, Division of Laguna. *Graduate studies and applied research, research journal* Volume 1.
- Burton, L. A. (2013). Mother tongue-based multilingual education in the Philippines: Studying top-down policy implementation from the bottom up. (Doctoral Dissertation), University of Minnesota, Minneapolis, MN.
- Davies, RJ & Dart, J. (2005). The most significant change (MSC) technique: A guide to its use.
- DepEd. (2012, February 17). DepEd order No. 16, s. 2012: Guidelines on the implementation of the mother Tongue-Based multilingual education (MTB-MLE). <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2012/02/17/do-16-s-2012-guidelines-on-the-implementation-of-the-mother-tonguebased-multilingual-education-mtb-mle/>
- Dutcher, N. (2001). Expanding educational opportunity in linguistically diverse societies. Washington, DC: Center for Applied Linguistics.
- Freeman, D. E., & Freeman, Y. S. (2000). Teaching reading in multilingual classrooms. Portsmouth, NH: Heinemann.
- Gaylo, P. J. B. (2020). Implementing Mother Tongue Based–Multilingual Education (Mtb-Mle): Outcomes And Challenges. *Review*, 148.
- Ghimire, L. (2012). Mother tongue instruction in multilingual schools of Nepal. *Nepalese Linguistics*, 27, 53-59.
- Gonzalez, A. (1996). Using Two/Three Languages in Philippine Classrooms: Implications for Policies, Strategies and Practices. *Journal of Multilingual and Multicultural Development*, 17 (2-4) , 210-218.
-

- Gonzalez, A. (2003) Language planning in multilingual countries: The case of the Philippines. Manila, Philippines: De La Salle University.
- Gorio, D. et al. (2014). Factors affecting the Implementation of the Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education as Perceived by Teachers in Baguio and Benguet. Retrieved last January 3, 2015 from <https://sites.google.com/site/languageandmothertongue/home/research-on-mtb-mle-implementation>.
- Kang, H.-S. (2012). English-only instruction at Korean universities: Help or hinderance to higher learning? *English Today*, 109, 29-34.
- Mahboob, A., & Cruz, P. (2013). English and Mother-Tongue-Based Multilingual Education: Language Attitudes in the Philippines. *Asian Journal of English Language Studies*, 1, 1-19.
- Medilo Jr, C. G. (2016, October). The experience of mother tongue-based multilingual education teachers in Southern Leyte, Philippines. In *International Forum Journal* (Vol. 19, No. 2, pp. 64-79).
- Nolasco, R., Datar, F. & Azurin, A. (2010). Starting where the children are: A collection of essays on mother-tongue based multilingual education and language issues in the Philippines. Quezon City: 170+ Talaytayan MLE Inc.
- Nolasco, Ricardo. (2009). 21 reasons why Filipino children learn better while using their mother tongue: A primer on Mother Tongue-based Multilingual Education (MLE) and other issues on language and learning in the Philippines. Diliman: Guro Formation Forum.
- Philippines Department of Education. (2009). Institutionalizing mother tongue-based multilingual education (Order no. 74). Pasig City: Author.
- Philippines Department of Education. (2012). Guidelines on the implementation of the mother tongue-based multilingual education (MTB-MLE) (Order no. 16). Pasig City: Author.
- Rosekrans, K., Sherris, A., & Chatry-Komareks, M. (2012). Education reforms for the expansion of mother-tongue education in Ghana. *International Review of Education*, 58(5), 593-618.
- Rueda, R., & Garcia, E. (1996). Teachers' perspectives on literacy assessment and instruction with language-minority students: A comparative study. *The Elementary School Journal*, 96 (3), 311-332.
- Tonio, J., & Ella, J. (2019). Pre-service Teachers' Attitudes towards the Use of Mother Tongue as Medium of Instruction. *Asian EFL*, 21(2.3), 231-253.